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Research Article

**GRANT SUPPORT OF PUBLIC INITIATIVES AS A TOOL FOR
RURAL DEVELOPMENT****Elena Belkina¹, Mariya Zaytseva¹, Tamara Tsatkhanova², Oleg Tsedinov², Elena
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Article Received: January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

The problem chosen by the authors for scientific research is undoubtedly relevant and is determined by the exacerbation of the issues of socio-economic development of rural areas. Determining the key areas of organizational and economic measures of state regulation of rural development is a necessity to overcome the protracted structural crisis in the countryside. In addition to the state, regions, municipalities, business structures and the local community should be involved in the implementation of state policy for the development of rural territories.

Key words: *rural areas, local initiatives, projects, grants.*

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INTRODUCTION:

The loss of domestic socio-economic destinations in the organization and implementation of agrarian relations by domestic rural areas, the gap in the standard of living between town and country can lead to unpredictable consequences for the economy and the social sphere.

To overcome the protracted structural crisis in the countryside, it is necessary from a new angle to look at the problems of the rural community in the context of developing new approaches, mechanisms and directions of state support and regulation. In addition to the state, regions, municipalities, business structures and the local community should also be involved in the implementation of state policy for the development of rural areas [4].

In accordance with the directions of the Strategy for the Sustainable Development of Rural Territories of the Russian Federation for the period until 2030 dated February 2, 2015, the priority goal of the government and local government is to develop the village and improve the quality of life of the rural population.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study of documents of territorial and sectoral strategic management of rural areas, allow to summarize the key directions of rural goal-setting, built in accordance with the logic and principles of sustainable development:

- creation of comfortable living conditions in rural areas, meeting the needs of the rural population, including

young families and young professionals in well-equipped housing;

- increasing the level of complex arrangement of settlements located in rural areas with objects of social and engineering infrastructure;

- stimulation of investment activity in the agro-industrial complex by creating favorable infrastructural conditions in rural areas;

- promoting the creation of high-tech jobs in the countryside;

- increased participation of citizens living in rural areas in the implementation of socially significant projects, grant support to local initiatives of citizens living in rural areas;

- formation of a positive attitude to the countryside and rural lifestyle - encouraging and popularizing achievements in the field of rural development [2].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

The universal composition of the directions of rural goal setting is contained in the State program "Development of agriculture and regulation of the markets for agricultural products, raw materials and food in the Krasnodar Territory". In 2013, the subprogram "Sustainable development of rural areas" is being implemented in the framework of the social direction in its pure form.

Table 1 reflects the degree of achievement of goals, the solution of tactical tasks for the sustainable development of rural territories of the Krasnodar Territory.

Table 1: Assessment the degree of achievement the target indicators of the subprogram "Sustainable development of rural areas"

Indicators	2015 г.		2016 г.		2017 г.	
	plan	fact	plan	fact	plan	fact
The volume of housing input for citizens living in rural areas, young families and young professionals, thousand m ²	11,7	12,8	10,5	10,9	8,915	11,71
The number of young families and young professionals who have improved housing conditions, families	162	164	101	145	162	171
Commissioning of general education organizations, places	264	264	-	-	-	-
Commissioning of midwifery stations and offices of general practitioners, units	-	-	-	-	6	6
Commissioning of a network of plane sports facilities, m ²	1000	1000	3000	3000	1000	3000
Commissioning of gas distribution networks, km	126	127,7	48,4	48,4	146	146
The level of gasification of residential buildings with gas in rural areas,%	76,2	76,2	76,2	76,2	76,2	76,2
Local water pipe commissioning, km	56,2	56,2	32,3	32,3	56,2	56,2
Level of provision of the rural population with drinking water,%	69,2	69,2	69,2	69,2	69,2	69,2
The number of settlements located in rural areas, in which projects of integrated arrangement of sites for compact housing development are implemented, units	-	-	-	-	1	0
Number of implemented projects of local initiatives of citizens living in rural areas who received grant support, units	1	0	-	-	1	0

The parametric assessment of the dynamics of the socio-economic development of rural territories of Krasnodar Region and the analysis of instruments of state stimulation of their development, allows us to

draw the following conclusions:

- the social portrait of a typical rural settlement in the Krasnodar Territory has the following features: small population (up to 500 people), the presence of the

minimum necessary infrastructure, high rates of "aging" of the population;

- infrastructure security is uneven; there are territories that are not equipped with drinking water, gas heating and sewer network;
- social infrastructure is equipped with every 4th settlement, which complicates the provision of basic services to residents of ultra-small and small villages;
- the structure of disposable resources has a predominantly monetary form, while the amount of incomes of the rural population is 1.5 times lower than the average value of the region;
- - Instrument-oriented documents are instruments of state stimulation of the development of socio-economic conditions for the functioning of rural territories;
- the priority of the state regional policy of sustainable development of rural areas is to improve the housing conditions of citizens living in rural areas, including young families and young professionals and the development of the engineering infrastructure of rural areas.
- insufficient in our opinion due to the increase in the rate of natural decline in the rural population is attention to the problems of social infrastructure development;
- passivity of the rural population in solving local problems;
- the mechanism for implementing projects of local initiatives of citizens living in rural areas does not work [1].

Rural areas of the Krasnodar Territory need a differentiated approach to regulating the parameters and vectors of their development, take into account regional aspects and be adapted to local characteristics. As an alternative tool for the implementation of municipal management at the level of rural areas, we propose to use the project approach. It involves the development and implementation of short-term projects with a differentiated target orientation in accordance with the prevailing functional orientation of rural areas. The project approach to the implementation of local initiatives was determined under the subprogram "Sustainable rural development" of the Krasnodar Territory State Program "Agricultural Development and Regulation of Agricultural Products, Raw Materials and Food Markets" in the form of grants to local rural communities for improving living conditions. This measure in the Krasnodar region has not received development.

The grant refers to state support funds provided from the federal and regional budgets on a non-reimbursable and non-repayable basis to a local government body or a territorial public self-government body of a rural settlement for the implementation of socially significant (non-commercial) projects with the participation of citizens living in rural areas. Table 2 presents the main components of the grant support for local citizens' initiatives.

Table 2: Main characteristics of the grant support for local initiatives of citizens living in rural areas

Characteristic	Value
Subjects	Rural territories of various levels, population, branches of social and economic spheres
Lines	Population of rural areas, socio-economic sphere
Grantees	- local governments of rural settlements
	- bodies of territorial public self-government of rural settlements
Stages	- analysis of "problem areas" of rural areas
	- study of implemented areas of support
	- initiation and development of projects or project portfolio
	- financial planning
	- project implementation
Priority directions for the implementation of directions	- evaluation of results, mistakes made and project closure
	- creation and arrangement of recreation areas, sports and children's playgrounds (creation and arrangement of parks, beaches, sports and children's playgrounds); engineering infrastructure objects
	- preservation and restoration of natural landscapes, historical and cultural monuments (cleaning of reservoirs, coastal zones, forest plantations, preservation and restoration of objects of cultural heritage)
Selection criteria:	- support of national cultural traditions, national crafts and crafts (creation of museums of peasant life, traditional crafts and crafts, development of rural tourism)
	- the project should be aimed at solving the most significant problem of a rural settlement in whose territory its implementation is planned, and meet the interests of a wide range of its representatives
- relevance	
- goal reachability	- the project objectives must be achievable within the framework of the project implementation, the objectives must be achievable
- compactness	- restriction of the project area to the borders of a rural settlement
- short term	- project implementation must be carried out within no more than one year

- low cost	- project implementation should not be associated with significant investments of funds not secured by sources of funding
- social partnership	- project initiators and other interested groups of the population should take part in the project implementation, including young people living in a rural settlement
- social effect	- project implementation should ensure improvement of the social environment

This financial measure of support from public authorities is a promising direction for the sustainable development of rural areas, as it provides for the consolidation of the financial resources of all participants: citizens, economic entities, local and regional budgets.

The implementation of this direction of supporting the sustainable development of rural areas implies an active interaction of the executive authorities with the population. It should be noted that more work up to 90% of all types of work related to the preparation, coordination, approval of all the required documentation for participating in the competition for a grant to support local initiatives of citizens living in rural areas falls on the local government of the rural settlement.

First of all, the administration of a rural settlement should inform the population about the possibility of participating in the competition, study the opinion of the population about the importance of the events and gather an initiative group participating in the project implementation. Participation in the project of residents of a rural settlement provides not only financial participation, but also labor participation, participation through the provision of equipment and materials for the performance of work.

To enhance the development of public participation in solving local issues, it is necessary to:

- 1) Develop pilot socially significant projects of initiatives, as a methodology for management;
- 2) To organize information propaganda among citizens and local governments of the benefits of participation in the implementation of this area of rural development;
- 3) To form the "Bank of social projects of citizens' initiatives" and place it on the official portal of the administration of Krasnodar Region.

As a pilot project, we have chosen one of the areas of grant support for citizens' initiatives - the creation and arrangement of a sports ground in x. Tamarovsky Brinkovsky rural settlement Primorsko-Akhtarskogo area.

The development of a socially significant non-commercial project involves the following actions:

- 1) Description of the problem and justification of its relevance to the public.

It is necessary to form a healthy lifestyle from an early age and maintain a lifetime. To this end, the state develops a sports infrastructure, promotes a healthy lifestyle, maintains and protects the health of citizens.

On the territory of x. Tamarovsky Brinkovsky rural settlement lives 618 people. Social facilities are represented by a general training school, a first-aid station, there is a rural house of culture, and a tent camp "Young Tourist" is functioning at the school base during the summer period. The remoteness of the farm from the district center of Primorsko-Akhtarsk is 45 km.

The sports infrastructure is represented by 2 sports facilities: a gym and a sports field at the school. The number of citizens who regularly engage in sports and physical culture of the total population is 128 people, which is 20.7% of the population. Every year, in accordance with the calendar plan of the settlement, mass sporting events are held in which about 170 residents of the settlement take part. The settlement has 2 sports sections: volleyball, chess.

In order to arrange the territory and popularize physical culture and sports among the population, as well as due to the lack of a sports ground in the settlement, the villagers decided to equip a comprehensive playground that includes a universal modern sports ground, namely:

- a platform for practicing table tennis;
- a platform of general physical training for adolescents and the older generation.

The site will be located in a green area near the school and the rural house of culture. It is planned to improve the territory of the sports ground: cut out and uproot the old, dangerous trees, trim the overgrown shrubs, plant trees and shrubs. The playground will have a special surface with markings for games, various modern game forms will be installed, a table for playing table tennis, a bicycle path for kids and teenagers 1.5 m wide will be installed, benches for rest and urns will be installed.

This project is aimed at all residents of a rural settlement and has no age limit. Its implementation will contribute to the psycho-emotional unloading of residents and will contribute to the promotion of a healthy lifestyle. On the sports ground for children there are new friends, games, children and adolescents get the basics of human relationships, learn to win and adequately lose, lose and win.

- 2) Development of a passport of a socially significant non-commercial project applying for a grant in 2019 (Table 3).

Table 3: General characteristics of the project

Indicator	Value
Direction of project implementation	Creation and arrangement of recreation areas, sports and children's playgrounds
Project name, address or location description	Creating a platform of general physical training in the x. Tamarovskom Primorsko-Akhtarskogo district of Krasnodar Territory
The project complies with the safety standards and legislation of the Russian Federation (yes / no)	Yes
Area on which the project is implemented, m ²	200
The purpose and objectives of the project	Purpose: creation of comfortable living conditions in rural areas. Objectives: the creation and arrangement of recreation areas, the construction of sports fields, the development of a network of plane sports facilities in the village, the promotion of public health
Initiator of the project	Sulimov A.G., Dorosheva O.V., Vasilchenko G.G. Vystupkin OM
Project Applicant	Administration of Brinkovsky rural settlement of Primorsko-Akhtarsky district
Duration of the project (the number of months, no more than 12)	3
Project start date	March 2018
Project End Date	May 2018
Total project costs, thousand rubles:	628,3
including at the expense of:	
grant	270,5
local budget	168,4
mandatory contribution of citizens, individual entrepreneurs and legal entities - total, thousand rubles	189,4
of them:	141,3
the contribution of citizens, thousand rubles:	-
in cash	141,3
labor participation	48,1
contribution of individual entrepreneurs, thousand rubles:	-
in cash	-
labor participation	48,1

To implement the project, it is planned to attract funds from the federal and regional budget in the amount of 270.5 thousand rubles, or 43% of the total expenditure need, 189.4 thousand rubles from the budget of the Brilinko settlement and 189.4 thousand rubles from citizens or 30.1% of the total need. Since the income level of rural residents is lower than the average salary

in the region, they suggested that they perform labor operations for this amount of expenses, which are connected with the preparation of the territory for the construction of the site.

3) Characteristics of the target group and project initiators (table 4).

Table 4: Characteristics of the target group and project initiators

Indicator	Value
Target group	
The number of rural population that confirmed participation in the project, people	56
Of these, young people under the age of 30	41
Population groups that will enjoy the results of the project	Дети, учащиеся МБОУ ООО № 14, молодежь, подростки туристического палаточного лагеря «Юный турист», жители сельского поселения
The number of people who will benefit directly and indirectly	280
including: - straight	220
- indirectly	60
Project initiators	
Sulimov A.G., Dorosheva O.V., Vasilchenko G.G. Vyspostkin OM, youth, young parents - project initiators	Active participation in the clearing and preparation of the site for construction
IP Lukyanov S.V.	Providing the necessary equipment for garbage collection and site preparation

Representatives of different age groups are involved in the project implementation, and joint activities will be a unifying factor. Individual entrepreneurs will also be attracted.

Table 5: The calendar plan for the implementation of project activities

Event name	Terms of implementation	Executive officer
Preparatory work: the dismantling of the coating, clearing of old trees and shrubs, area planning, garbage collection	March	Administration, schoolchildren, local residents (initiative group)
Repair and construction work: the device sports coverage, the installation of sports equipment	March-may	Contractor
Acquisition of equipment: "Rowing", "Upper" trainers, "Chest Press", "Press to chest", "Press legs", "Pendulum", "Elliptical", "Stepper", "Twister"; Sports complex with horizontal bars, bars and bench for the press, table tennis table I-4, benches (2 pieces), urn (2 pieces)	May	Contractor
Tidying up the surrounding area	May	Administration, local residents

Selection of a contractor is determined in the framework of the Federal Law of January 01, 2014. № 44 "On the contract system in the procurement of goods, works, services for state and municipal needs." As a result of the project implementation, a modern universal platform for general physical training will be created. This measure will allow attracting more children, adolescents, as well as adults to systematic physical culture and sports.

4) Justification of the effectiveness of the project.

The implementation of the proposed measures will allow to obtain a sustainable social effect expressed in the growth of the number of citizens systematically engaged in physical culture and sports, increasing the level of security of the population x. Tamarovsky plane sports facilities, which allows to improve their health, and in the future will allow us to get a healthy working-age generation.

The complex site and arrangement of its territory will

decorate the rural settlement, which will allow to draw public attention to the settlement's activities, increase the attractiveness of the territory for investors, in order to further develop the recreational opportunities of the rural settlement (the hamlet is located on the Azov Sea coast), improve the demographic situation.

The proposed pilot project for the creation and arrangement of a sports field emphasizes the main advantages of grant support to local initiatives of citizens as an effective tool for the development of rural areas, namely [3]:

- the achievement of maximum results is directly related to the fact that the planned activities are carefully selected, the need for their implementation is analytically justified and agreed with all the project participants;

- the qualitative characteristics of the activities are of priority, focusing on the high compliance of the results with the initially planned level allows to achieve the desired effect;

- strictly agreed operational terms of the project

approach protect all participants from temporary delays and the possible transfer of activities, projects aim to get quick visible results;

- effective management of the entire set of resources allows reducing risks and losses at all stages of the project.

CONCLUSION:

The development of practice-oriented tools, recommendations and approaches for their use by regional and local authorities in the development and implementation of strategic sectoral and territorial programs and local projects supporting the socio-economic development of rural areas will not only balance the parameters of social and economic development of the village, but also give im new functional status.

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